

Modifications de certaines réponses secondaires de stress chez *Dicentrarchus labrax* sous l'effet d'un β -bloquant à base de Carazolol. Application au transport

Modifications of some secondary stress responses in *Dicentrarchus labrax*, by the use of a β -blocker with a Carazolol base. Application to transport

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Abstract

A β -blocker with a Carazolol base was used by bath, and tested in 0⁺ sea-bass subjected to stress. In the first experiment, stress was induced by emptying the tank. In the second experiment, the compound was used during an imaginary 24-h transportation, and compared with MS 222.

The main modifications noted concern the erythrocytes and the osmotic pressure of the plasma. Compared with fish transported with MS 222 (15 mg/l), the fish subjected to the β -blocker (140 mg/l) had a larger number of red blood cells, in which the haemoglobin concentration (CCMH) was higher and the globular volume smaller. Their osmotic pressure and their chloraemia were lower, which seems to show a higher efficacy of the β -blocker in restricting failures of osmoregulation.